

A Study Of Tourism Potential In Igatpuri Tahasil Of Nashik District

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DOI-

Abstract

The study of this paper aims to study the various religious, Natural and cultural destination of Nashik District. Cultural, Natural tourism destinations (or pilgrim-towns as conventionally known) are special places where urbanization processes are driven by visitor influxes that visit these places for cultural and religious reasons.) Nashik boards of a large number of popular and revered religious cultural venues that are heavily frequented by locals as well as international tourists. Nashik has many religious cultural sites and pilgrimage places for different faiths. For this paper used secondary research methodology has been used for research for data collection, secondary data collected from, the literature the review also government agency data, tourism online news has been collected. This paper emphasizes the emergence of religious tourism in Nashik District and also explored the potential growth and suggested some solutions for development Igatpuri tourism in Nashik.

Keywords: Religious, Natural Tourism, Tourism Potential, Spiritual, Culture Tourism.

1.Introduction

India is a multi-destination country with a variety of tourist attractions and facilities. It is the second largest net foreign exchange earner by way of invisible exports. Tourism creates more jobs than any other sector for every rupee invested. It has a major role in promoting large-scale employment opportunities. Maharashtra States its tops in foreign tourist arrivals (20.8%) and counted among leading states for domestic tourists (7.2%). offers a variety of destinations for its tourists business, cultural-historical, geographical, and religious, etc. Tourism is travel for recreation, leisure, religious, family or business purposes, usually for a limited duration. Tourism is commonly associated with international travel, but may also refer to travel to another place within the same country. The World Tourism Organization defines tourists as people "traveling to and staying in places outside their usual environment for not more than one consecutive year for leisure, business and other purposes".

2.Objectives

1. To Study the Assessment of Tourism Potential Igatpuri Tahsil.
2. To Search New Tourism Centre / Places.
- 3.To Study the Historical and Natural Beauty Tourism Centre / Places in Igatpuri.

3.Hypothesis

- 1.There is scope and potential for further development of Tourism in Igatpuri Tahsil.
- 2.Igatpuri Taluka has a large number of Tourist Spots.
- 3.Socio-environmental factors are responsible for dynamic of Tourism Development.

4.Study Area

The Igatpuri tahsil has been selected for the study to present research work. The Igatpuri tehsil is located between 19°07' to 19°42' North latitude and between 73°33'E 73.55' east longitude at north western part of Maharashtra state. The total area extent of 2, 56000 Acer. Total population is 50,000 as per census 2001. Igatpuri is a beautiful hill station in Nasik District of Maharashtra. Igatpuri is a town and a Hill Station Municipal Council in Nasik District in the Indian State of Maharashtra. It is located in the Western Ghats. Igatpuri Railway Station Lies in Nasik District between Mumbai and Nasik Road on the Central Railway. Nasik to Igatpuri Distance between 45 k.m. Situated in the hills of Sahyadri's at a height of 1900 feet above sea level, it is popularly known as the queen of Sahyadri's. One of the less publicized hill stations of the state, it is 130 km from Mumbai. The Height of Igatpuri MSL is 1450 meter. Darna and Kadva River originated in Igatpuri taluka from Shenit Village. There are 125 Villages under in Igatpuri Tahsil as a Pimpri, Nandgaon, Borli,

IGATPURI TAHSIL LOCATION MAP

5. Methodology

Methodology is one of the important parts of analysis. Output or result of analysis highly depends on the methodology will be used for the data processing or analysis purpose. the following methodology will be adopted: -

The present Research study is based on primary and secondary data. primary data is collected from Field visit by the survey, Questionnaires & Interviews method. The secondary data collected through MTDC (Maharashtra Tourism development corporation), tourism reference books, Nasik District Gazetteer, local government offices, Gram Panchayat and Internet websites etc.

Step -I Primary data will be collected; exhaustive literature survey of the topic of investigation is to be undertaken. Published literature, reports will be collected from various libraries, Institutes and government departments etc. Besides this relevant literature will also reference books, bulletins, reviews will also be etc.by obtained through Internet.

Step -II various places were identified which having determinates of tourism potential of the Nashik city. Like as accessibility, health facilities, road, and infrastructure facilities, other entertainment facility

Step -II with the help of health facility, education facility, entertainment facilities

etc. tourism potential of Nashik city was assess.

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6. Tourism Centers In Igatpuri Tahsil
Tourism is the most significant segment of the Igatpuri's economy. Following are the places most visited by tourists:

1. Vipassana Meditation Center – Dhammagiri
2. Kasara ghat-
3. Bhavali Dam
4. Triangelwadi Fort
5. Kapildhara Tirth – Kavnai

1. Vipassana Meditation Center – Dhammagiri

Introduction

Vipassana, one of India's most ancient meditation techniques, is traced to Gautama the Buddha. It is the process of self-purification by self-observation. One begins by observing the natural breath to develop concentration and then moves on to observe the changing nature of body and mind and

experiences the universal truths of impermanence, suffering and ego lessness. Vipassana, which means, "to see things as they really are", is a logical and pure natural science. Its practitioners claim that as a by-product of mental purification, many psychosomatic diseases also get eradicated. With continued practice, the meditation relieves the tensions of everyday life and develops positive, creative energy for the betterment of the individual and society. Vipassana International Academy offers you an opportunity to learn the path to Dhamma - Gautama Buddha's technique of meditation. To learn Vipassana, it is necessary to take a ten-day residential course under the guidance of a qualified teacher. These courses are open to anyone who sincerely wishes to learn the technique. People from all

backgrounds find that they become better human beings. Thus, without conflict, it cuts across barriers of race, caste or religion, in any place, at any time and will prove equally beneficial to one and all. If you enroll for the retreat you will remain within the course site having no contact with the outside world for the duration of the retreat. You will follow a demanding daily schedule that includes about 10 hours of sitting meditation. You will also observe silence, not communicating with fellow students. There are three steps to the training.

Center Location

Dhammagiri is situated in the town of Igatpuri which is 45 k.m a way from Nasik and 136 k.m away from Mumbai on Mumbai –Agra Highway .it is well connected by Central railway Line.

2.Kasara ghat-

Also called as Thal Ghat or Thul Ghat is a ghat section (Mountain incline or slope) in the western ghats near the town of Kasara in Maharashtra. The Kasara Ghat is located on

the busy Mumbai – Nashik route, and is one of the four major routes, rail and road routes, leading into the Mumbai. The railway line, which passes through the Ghat is the steepest in India with a gradient of in 1 in 37

Bhavali Dam –

Bhavali Dam is an earthfall dam on river near Igatpuri, Nashik District in State of

Maharashtra in India. Bhavali Dam is Located near village Bhavali, Taluka Igatpuri, Nashik on Darna River tributary of

Godavari River. It is 8 Km. from Igatpuri and 52 Km. from Nashik. This is major earthen dam completed in 2011. The Length of the dam is 1157 m. and the length of the spillway is 58.00 m. Maximum height is 32.49 m. The Catchment area of dam is 25.90 sqkm and Gross storage is 1580 mcft and Irrigable command area is 4223 ha. out of which: 1263 ha. is in Igatpuri Taluka, Nashik & 2926 ha. from express canal in Ahmednagar and Aurangabad. There happen to be a lot of dams in the area. The Bhavali dam is situated very near once you have reached Igatpuri. Where the service road end, cross the highway and drive for around 6 kms through the village of Pimpri to reach it. The road is marked with green cultivated fields on both sides, stacks of hay, sunflowers

greeting you with their swaying smiles and bullock carts to make the picture complete. Once you climb up the dam steps, the beauty of the lake and the backdrop of the mountains has a pleasing effect. This is an ideal place for a picnic. The Maharashtra Tourism Development Corporation (MTDC) is planning to develop 23 acres of land near Bhavali dam as a tourist spot.

Centre Location - The dam is near Ghoti, 44 km away from Nashik.

Coordinates - 19.6350691°N 73.5906315°E **Coordinates.**

Owner - Government of Maharashtra, India

Height - 33.97 m (111.5 ft)

Length - 1,550 m (5,090 ft)

4. Triangelwadi Fort –

Sahyadri has spread one of its wings to the west in the Igatpuri region on which lie the forts like Kavnai, Balwant gad and Triangelwadi. The forts in this range have become easily accessible due to the construction of roads up to the hill-tops, the villages developed in this region and the frequent visits of people to this region. It is situated at an altitude of 3,000 feet above the sea level. Since it located very high the fort offers picturesque scenery of the whole locality, especially kulag and Kalsubai Mountain ranges. The fort Attracts trekkers

also. The top of the fort is shaped like a Turban. A temple dedicated to lord Hanuman is nearby an Architectural marvel; the fort can be accessed through a narrow pathway down to the Triangelwadi Lake. Situated about 6 km from rain forest Resort, Igatpuri, Just a few km away from Triangelwadi lake is Talegaon lake formed by the small Talegaon Dam. Situated at an altitude of 3,000 feet above the sea level. Triangelwadi fort at Igatpuri as an Architectural marvel. Entire locate of Igatpuri is nested by majestic Sahyadri's and Triangelwadi Fort is also be sieged by this Stunning Mountain

Ranges .Being in an Elevation Position ,this massive fort res house the picturesque scenery of the whole locality ,especially the view of the peaks from this fort is incomparable . The small path, which leads to the fortes itself kindle one's curiosity. It is amazing to notice that the surrounding area of this fort will be fully cultivated during the monsoon season and one have to voyage kilometers to reach to the base of this colossal structure. A magnificent temple dedicated to lord Hanuman maken a marvelous setting to this stunning fort. A Favorite Tourist Spot in the Igatpuri Region, Triangelwadi Fort also provides Excellent Opportunities Trekking

Centre Location –

One is expected to reach Igatpuri railway station, which is well connected by rail route

from Mumbai and Nasik. After exit from the station towards the S.T. stand end, there is a junction called Ambedkar Chowk before the S.T. stand. From this junction proceed along the route towards Vagholi col which is at a 30min. of walk. After moving down the col, a left turn takes us to the Tringalwadi village within half-an-hour.

Hiring jeep from Igatpuri to Tringalwadi village via Ghoti is also a good alternative to reach Tringalwadi village. Behind Tringalwadi village lies the Tringalwadi dam. After crossing the entire length of the dam wall, a road on the right leads us to the foothills of this fort. We come across 'Pandav Leni' as we approach the foothill of the fort. It takes about half-an-hour to reach the top of the fort.

5. Kapildhara Tirth – Kavnai

It is believed that Kapildhara Tirth is one of the ashrams of saint Kapil Muni. Along with Nasik. Kumbh mela is also held here in Kapildhara Tirth. Kapildhara Thirth this Place is some 15 km from Igatpuri, my native place. the Kumbh mela officially starts from this place it is believed that by Aadesh from "Shri swami Smartha Maharaj", shri Gajanan Maharaj (Shegaon) done tapasya for 12

Years and then become visible in Shegaon. Kumbh Mela happens in Nasik city after every 12 Years. But very few people know that before AD 1770 Kumbh Mela use to be organized in Kapil dhara Tirth, Kavnai. Kavnai is situated 50 Km from Nasik in Igatpuri Taluka. After AD 1770 the Peshwas shifted the Kumbh mela to Nasik and Trimbakeshwar. Sant Sri Gajanan Maharaj did meditation in Kapildhara Tirth for 12 years starting from AD 1866. Govt. of Maharashtra has given Grant for the development of this Tirth The Great Traveler

from China Hsuan Tsang we have studied in school history also visited this place and gave a big circular disk inside the Temple. There is also a Temple of Kamakshi Devi, which is under renovation the full area is surrounded by big Mountains Some time will come in Monsoons to visit when there will be lot of Greenery. Also visited, Ghatandevi Mata Mandir, which we usually visit every year in Navratri period. The Temples situated just starting of Ghat reaching to Kasara that's why the name Ghatandevi. The New temple was also under renovation. The Sahyadri range in Igatpuri region is mainly divided into Eastern range is known Kalsubai range comprising of Forts like. Kalsubai, kulang, Alang, Avoundha Patta while the eastern region includes Triangelwadi. Kavnai, Harihar, Brahmagiri and Anjeneri Forts. This region can be rambled over from Igatpuri to Ghoti village. The main entrance door of the fort still stands in a good condition. On entering the main door way, we can see a cave on the right and side. we have

go to via this route only to reach the fort top. on reaching the fort we can see a small pond towards southern side of the fort. There are many Dilapidated structures of mansion by the side of this pond. There is a Bastion at the western end of the fort. Also, a cistern is located near this bastion. Half an Hour sufficient to wonder over the fort top Kalsubai range, Trimbak range, Tringelwadi are some of the sightseeing points around the fort from over the fort top. Kavnai Fort lies to the right side of the base village. a snow of

the hill lands in the base village after half an hour of walk over this snow there is a right turn which leads us to a cleft. Simple rock climbing from here will take us to the main doorway of the fort .it takes about a hour to reach up to the main doorway from the base village

Center Location

Kapildhara – Kavnai is situated in the town of Igatpuri which is 40 k.m a way from Nasik and 136 k.m away from Mumbai on Mumbai –Agra Highway.

7.Result –

While Observing the Igatpuri Tourism we know that Igatpuri tehsil is Excellent Tourism Place Igatpuri Tahsil is known as specialize tourism tehsil. here, different tourism places are available for tourists all these places are joints by different transport ways. Also, different facilities are available. E.g.,” Vipassana meditation centre” on this tourism place is a very important Tourism Place in Igatpuri. Is this place is a International Tourism Centre in Maharashtra also. Igatpuri Tourism tehsil is known as a Tourism Tahsil. here one of the special features and is, in Igatpuri tehsil tourists gives visit in all Three seasons. Mostly tourist visited in winter and monsoon season because at that time Sahyadri mountain ranges, Spring fountains, Kasara ghat location is a very excellent climate are

founded. If government focus in Igatpuri as a Tourist Place by giving many facilities to Tourists. In Igatpuri Travel & Tourism related facilities like Hotels, Guides, Lodges, improve the level of Employment. There is some forts of history witness are also very excellent history of Igatpuri Tourism. In Igatpuri taluka there are 125 village under in Igatpuri tahsil. So, Many Tourisms centre’s in Igatpuri Developing because Good Employment Opportunities also increased. With the positive thinking we can also say that in Igatpuri we can develop many Tourism Places. Like Bhavali Dam. if we give different facilities for Tourists then it can be developed very well & Good e.g., Roads, Electricity, Water Boat club, Entertainment Things, Gymnasium, Musical fountains. If we really develop it then

all type of development takes place, like Economical, Development, Employment etc.

8. Conclusion -

1. Tourism at the End of Tourism we can say that Igatpuri Tahsil increasing Day by day.

2. With the positive thinking we can also say that in Igatpuri we can develop many Tourisms Places

ex.” Vipassana Meditation Center” is international tourism center in Tahsil

3. In the near western ghat Mountain ranges, Rivers, Fountains, Hot springs, Dam, lakes, pleatus is a welcome to Mumbai and Nasik Tourist.

4. In the Tahsil Historical, Natural and Cultural Tourist place are mostly founded.

5. In this Tourist mostly visited in winter and monsoon season because, climate, rainfall is very

Excellent attraction in tahsil.

6. Igatpuri is a One of the best places of Tourism.

7. Igatpuri Tahsil is a very good for located Tourism Activity.

8. In Igatpuri mostly Employment facilities are mostly increased day by day.

9. In Tahsil Tourism related Employment opportunities are also Increased day by day.

10. Tourism related information also mostly provided in the local peoples and Tourist.

11. In Tahsil Excellent Hotels are Founded MANAS Resorts, Ganaka motels, Mystic valley Resorts, Grand Ashwin is Three stars hotels are founded in tahsil.

12. “Ghatandevi Temple” is also famous tourist place in Igatpuri but, Many pollutions are founded in this near area. land pollution, soil pollution, water pollutions is a directly impact of Tourist Health. Any security, guide, lodging facility are not developed in near area.

13.” Tringelwadi Fort “is also Historical Place of Shivaji Maharaj at that time developed but, now in today this fort are not connected good road network facility. Water facility accommodation facility, Hotels and lodging facilities,

9. Suggestion -

1. Here basic facilities are also less we have to improve that facilities.

2. Solving the problems of pollution are mostly founded near place.

3. Try to keep every Tourists place pollution free place.

4. Tourism place in **Igatpuri** information data mostly distribute the people like as

through Newspapers, Tourism magazines, internet through, Communication network through reason for the attract the people of Igatpuri Tourism.

5. Tourist Attraction mostly developing required in the tourism centers like as Bhavli Dam is a very good nature of this Dam but now in today Boating facilities are not in developed, Employment facilities not developed, Transport network facilities are not good so, this place Government facilities required developing

6. Historical places forts to be developed for Tourism Attractions of Tourist.

7. Tracking, Adventure Tourism, Sports Tourism. So be To be improved required Of Government facilities like as MTDC Hotels, Dharmshalas, Lodging, Water facilities, Boating’s, Entertainment facilities.

8. Government to be given for local facilities – Water, Electricity’s, Educational Facility.

9. Local people given for Employment opportunities.

10. In tahsil Tourism centers near mostly pollution are founded, water pollution, soil pollution, Deforestation, Air pollution so Government stopping this pollution required.

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